

EVA

Berlin

2025

Electronic Media
and Visual Arts

March 12, 2025 - March 14, 2025
SU6 @ Fraunhofer Heinrich-Hertz-Institut
Salzufer 6, 10587 Berlin
Entrance Otto-Dibelius-Straße, 4th floor

Conference Programme

Day 1: AI and the Arts Wednesday, March 12: 9:00 am – 7:30 pm

08:45 am – 09:00 am Reception

09:00 am – 09:45 am Morning Refreshment

09:45 am – 10:00 am Conference Opening

10:00 am – 10:30 am Keynote 1:

Matteo Valleriani

Max Planck Institute for the History of Science

10:30 am – 12:00 pm Session 1:

Generative Identities

Matilde Gardini and Cristiana Bartolomei: From Concept to Reality: Analyzing the Role of AI in Architectural Visualization and Design

Katharina Weinstock: Memory, Ghosts and Trauma. AI-Generated Photorealism Beyond the Deepfake.

Abigail Rekas and Xinpeng Liu: Authorship and AI – Considering the Copyright Protection of AI Generated Materials

12:00 pm – 01:00 pm Lunch Break

01:00 pm – 02:45 pm Session 2:

CH between Draft and Signature

Ilan Manouach: Generative Palimpsests: The Feature Space of Synthetic Comics

Mar Morosse: Artificial Intelligence and Art History: Exploring New Dimensions in Cultural Analysis

Julio Velasco: AI in Artistic Creation: Tool, Gadget, or Aesthetic (R)evolution – Text/Image Platforms

Sofia Menconero and Leonardo Baglioni: AI and Landscape Painting: Perspective and Augmented Reality in Perugino's Annunciazione Ranieri

02:45 pm – 03:15 pm Coffee Break

03:15 pm – 05:00 pm Session 3:

Connected to the Machine

Isabelle Hamm: Generative AI and Art Mediation: Exploring Personalization, Participation, and Shared Experiences

Slawomir Nikiel: Concept Art Design and Generative Artificial Intelligence

Karam Al-Janabi, Hendrik Appel, Brian Eschrich, Robert Fischer, Maria Matthes and Monika Reich: Discussing AI with AI – Interacting with a Chatbot System

Brian Eschrich, Robert Fischer, Maria Matthes, Kelsang Mende and Monika Reich: Exploring Virtual Reality in an Exhibition Context/Virtual Reality Demonstrator

05:00 pm – 05:30 pm Coffee Break

05:30 pm – 07:30 pm

Exhibition, Performances

Eva Waldherr werk5 GmbH

Andrea de Polo Saibanti Zeuschel GmbH

Gerhard Schnittger Verus Digital GmbH

Monika Reich TU Dresden

Robert Fischer TU Dresden

Day 2: CH Digitally Formatted

Thursday, March 13: 9:00 am – 9:30 pm

08:45 am – 09:30 am

Reception and Morning Refreshment

09:30 am – 11:15 am Session 1:

Memory Twins I

Marinos Ioannides, Elena Karittevli, Panayiotis Panayiotou and Drew Baker: Beyond Digital

Twins: Introducing the Memory Twin for Cultural Heritage

Yinhua Chu: Digital Ghosts: Flusser, Vampyroteuthis, and Li Yi-Fan's Virtual Memories

Zijing Song and Christian Wagner: The Virtual Time Machine: An Artistic Exploration with Generative Artificial Intelligence in Heritage Practices

Andrea de Polo Saibanti: Using Kitodo for digitizing your resources

11:15 am – 11:45 am Coffee Break

11:45 am – 01:00 pm Session 2:

Memory Twins II

Benjamin Feder and Daniel Johannes Meyer:

ToHyVe: Walkable 360° Videos for Hybrid Formats

Alessandro Basso, Caterina Palestini, Maurizio

Perticarini and Giovanni Rasetti: D(A)nte's

(I)nferno Representations Through Integrated A.I.

and Parametric Drawing Techniques.

Tina Schneider, Jasper Funk-Smit and Jens

Dobberthin: Transformation of a Dor Beetle –

from a Scientific Collection Object to a Multimedia,

Hybrid, Interactive and Barrier-free Experience

01:00 pm – 02:00 pm Lunch Break

02:00 pm – 3:30 pm Session 3:

On Display – Experiencing the New Museum

Ulf Beyschlag: Mobile Museum

Francesca Fatta and Paola Raffa: From

Museum to Theater Digital Humanities Tools

towards include and Cultural Fruition

Roberta Spallone, Chiara Teolato, Michele

Russo, Marco Vitali, Valerio Palma, Enrico

Pupi and Martina Rinascimento: Visualising

Piffetti's Library in Villa Della Regina Museum:

An Interdisciplinary Digital Project for Knowledge

Accessibility

03:30 pm – 04:00 am Coffee Break

04:00 pm – 05:45 pm Session 4:

CH In Conversation

Thomas Weibel: The Antikythera Mechanism:

Data Visualisation using Web-based Virtual

Reality

Riccardo Rapparini: Broadcasting Architecture

in the Age of New Media. Innovative Tools for

Changing Times

Laura Farroni and Matteo Flavio Mancini: Data

Transformation for Narratives Context: From

Scientific Research to its Communication

Francesco Stilo and Lorella Pizzonia: The

Famedio by Leone Savoja at the Monumental

Cemetery of Messina

05:45 pm – 06:15 pm Keynote 2:

Joachim Bauer

University of Freiburg

06:30 pm – 08:00 pm Introduction to the HHI

Visit of Forum Digital Technologies (FDT) and

of Innovation Center for Immersive Imaging

Technologies (3IT) at Science Tech Space @

Fraunhofer Heinrich-Hertz-Institut, just a five-minute

walk away.

08:00 pm – 09:30 Social Event

Buffet and drinks, followed by an open-ended get

together.

Day 3: Hybride Realities

Friday, March 14: 9:00 am – 5:00 pm

08:45 am – 09:30 am Reception and

Morning Refreshment

09:30 am – 11:00 am Session 1:

Knowledge Architectures

Domenic Städtler: Authority Files for Search and

Filter Options in the German Digital Library

Angela Kailus: Minimum Record Recommendation

for Museums and Collections

Frithjof Schwartz and Björn Böhme: Virtual

Models from the Ego Perspective. A Development

for Comparative Perception

11:00 am – 11:30 am Coffee Break

11:30 am – 01:00 pm Session 2:

CH Digitally Reproduced

Enrico Pupi and Piergiuseppe Rechichi.

Optimizing Inference Conditioning Techniques

In Image Generation For Participatory Urban

Transformation.

Lisa Pfeiffer: ELIO: Innovations is Object

Digitalization and Business Models in the Cultural

Sector

Ruth Reiche: Grimm4Geeks: Art meets Digital

Humanities or an exploratory approach to Artistic

Data Visualization using the example of the

Children's and Household Tales of the Brothers

Grimm

01:00 pm – 02:00 pm Lunch Break

02:00 pm – 03:30 pm Session 3:

What's on in Berlin

Benjamin Feder and Daniel Johannes Meyer:

DOMEconnect – Interactive Live Streaming

Connecting Immersive Venues

Andreas Bienert: SHIFT MetamorphoSis of

cultural Heritage Into augmented hypermedia

assets For enhanced accessibiliTy and inclusion

Lyubov Dimova, Dominik Lengyel: The New

Tactile Model of Pergamon for Berlin

Jacopo Spinelli, Dominik Lengyel: The Visual

Identity of a Conference between Science, Art,

Museums and Technology

03:30 pm – 04:00 pm Coffee Break

04:00 pm – 04:30 pm Keynote 3:

Dirk Hagen

Hannover University of Applied Sciences and Arts

04:30 pm – 05:00 pm

Conference Closing Remarks